

FRAMEWORK FOR IMPROVING QUALITY OF LIFE FOR PERSONS LIVING WITH A RARE DISEASE

INTRODUCTION

Rare Diseases International (RDI) launched a groundbreaking initiative to develop a comprehensive framework aimed at improving the quality of life for individuals living with a rare disease. This effort aligns with the principles of Universal Health Coverage (UHC), ensuring that no one is left behind in accessing essential healthcare services. As the global community anticipates the forthcoming World Health Organization (WHO) Resolution on Rare Diseases and its related Global Action Plan, RDI recognizes the urgent need for a structured, inclusive approach to inform policymakers.

WHO defines Quality of Life as *“an individual's perception of their position in life in the context of the culture and value systems in which they live and in relation to their goals, expectations, standards and concerns”* (WHO, 1997). This definition highlights the multidimensional concept that encompasses physical and psychological well-being, level of independence, social relationships, and personal beliefs. RDI members consider that quality of life for Persons Living With a Rare Disease (PLWRD) rests on three interconnected pillars: **physical well-being**, **mental well-being**, and **being an active member of society**. The purpose of this framework is not to establish a new definition of quality of life, but rather to explore what it means for PWLRD. It emphasizes the importance of social participation and belonging, and highlights that the individual's own perception of their well-being must be central to any discussion or intervention aimed at improving quality of life. This understanding is equally relevant for PLWRD, while emphasizing the importance of ensuring they have access to the necessary resources and support to live fulfilling lives.

By drawing on the expertise and lived experiences of RDI members and partners, this framework will provide critical insights to shape effective policies, address gaps in care, and drive meaningful change for the rare disease community worldwide.

OBJECTIVES

This initiative addresses the absence of a guiding document focused on improving the quality of life for PLWRD. The primary phase objective is to develop a framework informed by insight and priorities of RDI community and partners. In a second phase, we aim to enrich the framework with practical guidance based on archetype context and scenarios. The proposed framework aims to reflect a person's journey with a rare disease, creating a flexible and adaptable framework that accommodates various aspects of life.

- **Developing an RDI framework to support PLWRD and their families.**
- **Informing decision-makers and stakeholders through global action plans.**
- **Addressing multiple challenges and identifying key areas of impact.**

FRAMEWORK DEVELOPMENT AND CONSULTATION PROCESS

This framework was developed through a collaborative and iterative process involving RDI members and key stakeholders. Initial activities included scoping and consultation with RDI's International Federation members to identify approaches and challenges relevant to improving the quality of life for PLWRD. A dedicated workshop was held during the in-person RDI Membership Meeting 2024 in Barcelona to gather further input and validate early directions.

These engagements contributed to the identification of concrete areas that stakeholders can undertake activities to improve the well-being of PLWRD. The diversity of rare diseases and regional differences made it essential to adopt a flexible framework approach, one that countries and regions can adapt to their specific strengths and needs.

The framework reflects the feedback received through a wide consultation process. Input provided by RDI members has been carefully incorporated, ensuring that the perspectives of the rare disease community are embedded throughout the document.

KEY ELEMENTS OF THE FRAMEWORK

Diagnosis & Treatment	Access to Healthcare Services	Access to diagnosis, decreasing gap in diagnosis time
		Access to treatment
	Continuity & Coordination of Care	Access to integrated, multidisciplinary care
		Better transition between pediatric to adolescent to adulthood
Supportive & Specialized Care	Development of standard care guidelines	
	Pain management	
Healthcare System & Infrastructure	Availability of rehabilitation support	
	Accessibility of healthcare facilities; transportation	
Mental Health & Wellbeing	Biopsychosocial & Mental Health Support	Reimbursement of services
		Mental health support
	Awareness & Social Recognition	Peer support
Social Integration	Social Inclusion	Reducing stigma
		Recognition of Person Living with a Rare Disease
	Accessibility Design	End social isolation
Social Protection	Inclusive education & employment	Safe environment & online
		Accessibility tools & Universal Design
	Family & Caregiver Support	Spiritual support
Education	Public Awareness & Perception	Inclusive, access to education (zero rejections)
		Acceptance at workplace
	Knowledge Sharing	Equal work and equal pay
Professional Training		Job skills
Policy & Advocacy	Healthcare Infrastructure & Systems	Support service for Family or Caregiver
		Starting a family
	Policy & Governance	Social services
		Awareness of the public
Healthcare Infrastructure & Systems	Disease-specific and all RDs	
	Relevant research for PLWRD and caregivers	
Policy & Governance	Rare Disease Policy	
	Protection under law	
Healthcare Infrastructure & Systems	National health plans on RD	
	Accountability of Government, PLWRD, PAGs	

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MACRO AREAS OF THE FRAMEWORK

A. Diagnosis and Treatment

The diagnosis and treatment aspect emphasizes the importance of early and accessible diagnosis, timely interventions, and patient-centered care. It also stresses the need for engaging individuals in their care plans, ensuring smooth transitions across different life stages, integrating multidisciplinary approaches, and prioritizing pain management and rehabilitation. Telemedicine platforms offer a powerful tool to enhance remote access to healthcare, particularly for those living in underserved or remote areas. Strengthening the connection between existing networks allows knowledge and expertise to travel, rather than the patient, thus improving efficiency and reducing the burden on individuals and families. Moreover, structural aspects such as transportation for healthcare access and better reimbursement policies are identified as critical for improving overall healthcare experiences.

B. Mental Health & Wellbeing

Mental health support helps address the emotional and biopsychological challenges that often accompany rare diseases, providing individuals with the tools to navigate their daily lives. Reducing stigma is essential to fostering a more inclusive society, ensuring that those with rare diseases are treated with dignity and respect. Awareness campaigns in educational institutions and workplaces can play a key role in dismantling misconceptions, promoting empathy, and normalizing conversations around rare diseases and mental health. Recognition of PLWRD validates their experiences and promotes actions that address their unique needs. It is equally important to acknowledge that caregivers also face substantial social, psychological and economic pressures, and must be supported through dedicated services and policies that address their multidimensional needs. Peer support plays a vital role in creating a sense of community, allowing individuals to connect with others who share similar experiences.

MACRO AREAS OF THE FRAMEWORK

C. Social Integration

Improving quality of life through social integration requires breaking down barriers that lead to isolation and fostering a sense of belonging and inclusion. Addressing social isolation means creating opportunities for meaningful engagement in communities, both in-person and online, ensuring safe and welcoming environments. Accessibility tools, such as ramps, braille, and assistive technologies, are essential in enabling full participation, while universal design principles must be applied to public transport, buildings, and shared spaces to make them inclusive for all. Beyond physical access, fostering hope and faith can empower PLWRD, offering emotional resilience and a sense of purpose. By prioritizing these elements, society can build a more inclusive and supportive environment where PLWRD can thrive socially and emotionally.

D. Social Protection

Enhancing social integration for individuals living with a rare disease requires a framework that promotes inclusion, accessibility, and equal opportunities across all aspects of life. Ensuring zero rejection policies in education is crucial to providing every child the right to learn and develop their potential. In the workforce, fostering acceptance, equal pay for equal work, and job skill development helps create an inclusive job market where individuals with rare diseases can thrive. Beyond employment, social services must be strengthened to provide essential resources and support networks, ensuring long-term well-being. Families also play a vital role in social integration, requiring dedicated support services, assistance with starting a family, and caregiver reimbursement to ease financial and emotional burdens.

MACRO AREAS OF THE FRAMEWORK

E. Education

Raising public awareness about rare diseases is essential to fostering understanding and reducing stigma. PLWRD is just like anyone else; their condition may be uncommon, but they are not defined by it. Education efforts should emphasize both disease-specific knowledge and broader awareness of all rare diseases, highlighting common challenges and misconceptions. Sharing lived experiences plays a crucial role in humanizing these conditions, helping the public and medical professionals recognize the real-life impact of rare diseases. Additionally, educating healthcare professionals (HCPs) is vital to improving diagnosis, treatment, and patient care, ensuring that PLWRD receive timely and effective medical support.

F. Policy and Advocacy

A strong policy and advocacy framework is essential for improving the quality of life. A Rare Disease Policy should provide legal protection, guaranteeing the rights of PLWRD and promoting inclusion in national health plans. Establishing dedicated Rare Disease Centers ensures access to specialized care, research, and support services. An electronic protocol for registering and monitoring PLWRD can streamline diagnosis, treatment, and data collection, while ensuring that medical records and essential medicines are readily available. Governments, alongside patient advocacy groups (PAGs), PLWRD and stakeholders would be accountable for implementing and enforcing these policies to ensure improvement in the quality of life.

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About Rare Diseases International

RARE
DISEASES
INTERNATIONAL

Rare Diseases International (RDI) is the global alliance of People Living with a Rare Disease (PLWRD) of all nationalities across all rare diseases. Representing over 120 organizations on 6 continents, RDI's mission is to be a strong common voice on behalf of rare disease patients around the world, to advocate for rare diseases as an international public health priority and to represent and empower its members.

RDI is a registered non-profit organization incorporated under French law on 9 October 2018. RDI has been operating since 28 May 2015 as an informal network of rare disease patient organisations to form the global alliance representing patients and families. In 2024, RDI became a Non-State Actor in official relations with the WHO.

<https://www.rarediseasesinternational.org/>